

CRIMINOLOGICAL CLASSIFICATION OF SOME CRIMES THAT OCCUR IN THE FAMILY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7841810>

Abstract: This article analyzed the criminological classification of certain crimes that occur in the family.

Keywords: Family, society, Constitution, Criminal Code, crimes, criminology.

Family is the main unit of society. It is a source that ensures the continuity of generations, preserves our sacred traditions, including nurturing children and influencing the future life of the country and society. For this reason in our country, we pay special attention to the family values. This is also reflected in our national legislation. Chapter 14 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan is directly devoted to the family. In addition, the Criminal Code establishes liability for offenses committed in the family and against the family.

Family crimes refer to crimes committed by one member of the family against other members of the family. [1,502] Various crimes are committed in the family (emotional, sexual and other). However, crimes committed by one family member with the use of violence against another family member prevail among them, including a mother against her own child and other types of crimes against children.

Family crimes are caused by the quarrel between family members and the environment in which he lives. Crimes committed with force in the family is the problem of society from around the world. This bias in criminology of family relations in foreign countries is called "home violence" ("family violence"). [2,162] The importance of this problem is that the majority of crimes that are committed using violence are mainly handled in the family. Crimes committed in the family in most cases are dealt with by the husband (woman) towards the woman (husband).

In general, the problem of domestic violence is less pronounced than the problem of general violence. Not only politicians and scientists, but women's and girls' actions and actions that protect children's interests are of great importance to the fact that this problem has become a subject of addition.

Explaining the concept of violence is not only a difficult issue, but perhaps there is no solution, because most of the situations we encounter in our daily life are related to the use of violence, but we accept them as a normal phenomenon (for example, children physical punishment). All over the world, most families use violence against children, which is classified as a crime against the person. The coercion used to exercise leadership by performing assigned tasks in the family (for example, fulfilling parental duties, exercising rights related to education, etc.) has a legal character. Exceeding the limits of these rights and publicizing such actions will lead to sanctions against the culprits. In this case, the guilty behavior is determined by the damage caused to the victim's body (injury). Including, the use of coercion can be seen in verbal form, psychological influence, in the performance of minor duties (for example, separating the husband or wife from material power). When adults use violence against children in the family, they do not always realize that they are breaking the criminal law with their actions,

according to the behavior that has been formed for centuries. Many of these crimes, especially if they do not cause harm to the human body or the health of the victim, remain unknown to those around them and do not lead to appropriate measures.

According to the research conducted in the world, the use of violence against children is approved by the majority of people. For example, the Hori survey conducted in Germany (1968) shows that 85% of the people consider hitting children as means of raising children. Two years later, this figure decreased slightly (75%). In the United States, there are 5.7 cases of physical, sexual, or sexual abuse per 1,000 people under the age of 18 each year. According to experts, 0.5-2.5 mln. the elderly suffer from oppression. [3,176]

Crimes of different nature and severity are dealt with using violence. Crimes against human life and health (in particular, murder and intentional bodily harm), crimes against sexual freedom of a person are leading among them. For example, in Russia, about 12,000 family homicides are committed every year, of which about 60% are the murder of a husband (wife), which is more than 25% of all homicides committed in the country. [4,503]

In most countries, women are more likely to be victims of family violence than men. However, in some countries, the opposite is observed (for example, in Hurricane). If in the second half of the 70s of the 20th century, the ratio of victimized women to victimized men was approximately 7.1, in the 90s, this indicator was 3.1, which means that the criminal activity of women in the family increased.

One of the crimes committed by violence in the family - the crime of killing a wife (husband) by a husband (wife) is distinguished by three types:

1) A husband's (woman's) abduction of a woman (husband) with the intention of covetousness. This type of homicide makes up 5% of crimes related to the killing of a woman by her husband. The motive for killing a person with the intention of greed can be to get rid of the alimony payment, to occupy the area of the shelter, and to accelerate the inheritance. A husband's (woman's) shaving of his wife's (husband's) may also be related to "marriage fraud". In this case, the swindler enters into marriage in order to take possession of the woman's (husband's) property, and after that he gets an inheritance.

2) Husband's (woman's) divorce of his wife (husband) in order to free himself from various jobs (about 5%). The list of such tasks can include the need to constantly look after a sick or elderly woman (husband) or contact her in another way. Such killings can also be used in cases where the husband (woman) wants to enter into a new marriage (if the woman (husband) does not agree to the annulment of the marriage). Such murders are always deliberate, they are very well planned. Therefore, their level of secrecy is very high

3) Husband's (woman's) divorce due to jealousy (more than 50%). Such murders are usually carried out in cases where a woman (husband) has committed rape. In some cases, this type of murder may be dealt with under the influence of suspicion.

Jealousy murders are committed more by men than by women. The circumstances of killing a woman in order to take revenge on her husband are very important. Women who have been abused and humiliated by their husbands for a long time do not always turn to the law enforcement agencies. When the time comes, they start looking for ways to get rid of their cruel husband. In some cases, they decide to kill.

Crimes against a person's sexual freedom can also be committed in the family. Women often suffer here. In addition, sexual abuse of minor children (mostly stepdaughters and children),

crimes against their normal physical and mental development, sexual intercourse with a minor and other similar criminal offenses are dealt with. According to US scientists, about 2 million American women were victims of similar crimes in their childhood. [5,165]

In order to prevent crimes in the family, the adoption of targeted programs such as "Family Planning", "Protection of Motherhood and Childhood", "Difficult Teenagers", "Fathers and Children" reflects the important directions of family policy.

It is necessary to develop the legislation on the family, taking into account the living conditions that are currently being implemented. In particular, in the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, criminal punishment for domestic violence should be established, the system of protection of women and children should be strengthened, in order to prevent crimes in the family, to break the psychological immunity of children against the use of violence in the family from the kindergarten age, to raise them in the spirit of respect for adults and children, stress In some cases, it is necessary to learn how to control emotions. It would be appropriate to further improve the work of community adjustment centers for victims of crimes committed using force in our republic.

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